

Real-time Cyclostationary Analysis for Cognitive Radio via Software Defined Radio

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Abstract—Cyclostationary analysis such as spectral correlation function (SCF) and spectral coherence function (SOF) has been accepted as an important tool in signal detection and radio frequency (RF) parameter estimation in cognitive radios. However, cyclostationary analysis requires extremely high resolution to fully observe the cyclic frequency features, leading to very high computational complexity and difficulty in real time implementation, especially on software defined radios where computational capability is limited. In this paper, we implement and demonstrate a real time SCF/SOF RF signal analyzer by adopting previously proposed two-stage dynamic resolution SCF/SOF estimation method using software defined radios. Specifically, high resolution SCF/SOF calculation is only performed near the expected cyclic feature locations obtained through a low complexity coarse estimation employing spectral analysis. This cyclostationary analysis based RF signal analyzer is capable of sensing the existence of primary users and estimating the carrier frequency and symbol rate accurately. Using Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) software defined radio platform and GNU radio software, we implement and demonstrate such a cyclostationary analysis based RF signal analyzer in real time and validate the performance in realistic wireless communication channels.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cognitive radio [1] (CR) and dynamic spectrum access [2] (DSA) technologies have attracted lots of interests recently to solve the “spectrum draught” problem [3] and improve the spectrum utilization efficiency. Three types of cognitive radio have been proposed [1][4][5]. Most of existing cognitive radio research is based the overlay cognitive radio shown in Fig. 1(a). In overlay cognitive radios, secondary users utilize the spectrum holes where there is no primary user transmission to avoid interference from/to the primary users and co-exist with the primary users. Hence, in overlay cognitive radio, spectrum sensing is first performed to find primary user transmissions and spectrum holes. In comparison, underlay cognitive radio (shown in Fig. 1(b)) transmits an ultra-wideband signal with a predetermined spectrum mask specified by the Federal Communication Commission (FCC). Since the power spectral density (PSD) of the spectrum mask is so low that it’s even under the noise floor, the underlay cognitive radio can co-exist with the primary users without causing harmful interference and without doing any spectrum sensing. As a direct result of lacking spectrum sensing and the low PSD of transmission, underlay cognitive radio does not provide high spectrum

efficiency and is not as attractive as its overlay cognitive radio counterpart.

Fig. 1. Cognitive Radios

A more sophisticated cognitive radio that combines overlay CR and underlay CR, namely hybrid overlay/underlay cognitive radio (shown in Fig. 1(c) [4][5]) has been proposed recently to maximize the spectrum utilization of cognitive radio. In hybrid overlay/underlay CR, the secondary user transmits according to a dynamic spectrum mask (instead of a fixed spectrum mask as in underlay CR). The major difference and benefit of hybrid overlay/underlay CR is that it can transmit RF signals in active primary user band. Compared with overlay CR where no transmission is allowed in active primary user bands, the hybrid overlay/underlay CR obviously takes advantage of more spectrum. As long as the PSD in such active primary user band is lower than the interference tolerance threshold, no harmful interference is caused to the primary user. Since this interference tolerance threshold is a dynamic one determined by the current network condition, secondary users is able to transmit higher PSD than predetermined spectrum mask, leading to higher throughput than underlay CR.

However, in hybrid overlay/underlay CR, a mere detection of the existence of primary users (and spectrum holes) is not enough. In addition to normal spectrum sensing performed

in overlay CR, the hybrid overlay/underlay CR transceiver needs to accurately estimate important RF parameters of the primary users to adaptively adjust its transmission waveform to co-exist with primary users. Such parameters may include, and are not limited to, the carrier frequency, symbol rate and modulation type. We call such a sophisticated RF signal analyzer Intelligent Spectrum Sensing engine. Fig. 2 illustrates such an intelligent spectrum sensing engine.

Fig. 2. Intelligent Spectrum Sensing

Cyclostationary analysis has been accepted as effective tool for electronic emission detection [6][7], signal detection and spectrum sensing [8][9], RF parameter estimation [10], and modulation detection [11][12][13][14]. However, cyclostationary-based signal processing algorithm such as spectral correlation function (SCF) and spectral coherent function (SOF) requires extremely high resolution to fully observe the cyclic frequency features. Hence, the computation complexity is high and it is difficult to perform such algorithms in real time, especially on software defined radios where computational capacity is limited.

In this paper, we implement and demonstrate a real time SCF/SOF RF signal analyzer by adopting previously proposed two-stage dynamic resolution SCF/SOF estimation method using software defined radios [10]. Specifically, high resolution SCF/SOF calculation is only performed near the expected cyclic feature locations obtained through a low complexity coarse estimation. This cyclostationary analysis based RF signal analyzer is capable of sensing the existence of primary users and estimating the carrier frequency and symbol rate accurately. Moreover, this SCF/SOF RF signal analyzer can also be used to identify and classify the modulation type of the primary user signals [10][15], but this is out of the scope of this paper and will be reported in future publications. Specifically, using arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), wireless channel emulator (WCE), and USRP software defined radios [16], we validate and demonstrate the proposed RF signal analyzer in real time. Employing this RF signal analyzer, the performance of our software defined radio based cognitive radio [17] is also significantly improved.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In section II, we briefly review the SCF and SOF analysis. Section III discusses the implementation of SCF/SOF analysis for cognitive radio network. Section IV illustrates the experiment and real-time demonstration. Conclusion and future work are given in Section V.

II. REVIEW OF SPECTRAL CORRELATION/COHERENCE FUNCTION ANALYSIS

Modulated signals have built-in periodic features due to the modulated data are coupled with symbol rate, carrier or cyclic prefix, etc. A signal $x(t)$ is considered to be cyclostationary in wide sense if

$$m_x(t + T_0) = m_x(t) \quad (1)$$

$$R_x(t + T_0, u + T_0) = R_x(t, u) \quad (2)$$

where T_0 is the period of mean m_x and autocorrelation R_x . We can also rewrite (2) in Fourier series as [18][19]:

$$\begin{aligned} R_x(t, \tau) &= R_x(t + \tau/2, t - \tau/2) \\ &= E\{x(t + \tau/2)x^*(t - \tau/2)\} \\ &= \sum_{\alpha} R_x^{\alpha}(\tau) e^{j2\pi\alpha t} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where α is the cyclic frequency which can be extracted and used as features for identifying transmitted signals [20], and $R_x^{\alpha}(\tau)$ denotes the cyclic autocorrelation function (CAF), which is given by

$$R_x^{\alpha}(\tau) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} R_x(t, \tau) e^{-j2\pi\alpha t} dt \quad (4)$$

when $R_x(t, \tau)$ is periodic in t with period T_0 , (4) can be expressed as [15]:

$$R_x^{\alpha}(\tau) = \frac{1}{T_0} \int_{-T_0/2}^{T_0/2} R_x(t, \tau) e^{-j2\pi\alpha t} dt \quad (5)$$

The Fourier transform of the CAF is defined as the Spectral Correlation Function (SCF), which is given by:

$$S_x^{\alpha}(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R_x^{\alpha}(\tau) e^{-j2\pi f \tau} d\tau \quad (6)$$

SCF can be measured by the normalized correlation between two spectral components of $x(t)$ at $f + \frac{\alpha}{2}$ and $f - \frac{\alpha}{2}$ over Δt interval. Then, the ideal measurement of SCF can be expressed as:

$$S_X^{\alpha}(f) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_{-\Delta t/2}^{\Delta t/2} \frac{1}{T} X_T \left(t, f + \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) X_T^* \left(t, f - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) dt \quad (7)$$

where finite time Fourier transform of $x(t)$ is

$$X_T(t, f) = \int_{t-T/2}^{t+T/2} x(u) e^{j2\pi f u} du \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 illustrate the theoretical SCFs of a BPSK modulated signal and a QPSK modulated signal, respectively. From these two figures, we can observe that (1) for the SCF of BPSK signal, there are four peaks, two appear at $f = 0$ and $\alpha = 2f_c$, and other two appear at $\alpha = 0$ and $f = f_c$; (2)

Fig. 3. The SCF of BPSK Modulation

Fig. 4. The SCF of QPSK Modulation

for the SCF of QPSK signal, there are two peaks at $\alpha = 0$. The two peaks in the cyclic frequency domain at $f = 0$ and $\alpha = 2f_c$ disappear in the SCF of QPSK signal because the in-phase and quadrature components of QPSK signal create cyclic frequency peaks with different sign and cancel each other out. It is obvious that when $\alpha = 0$ the SCF reduces to the power spectrum density (PSD) of the signal. It is important to note that both Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 are generated from a large amount of data. In reality, we can only obtain a short length of RF signal to perform SCF and the in-phase and quadrature components of QPSK signal would not entirely cancel each other's cyclic frequency peaks out. Hence, we will still observe two smaller peaks in the cyclic frequency domain in the SCF of QPSK signals.

A significant benefit of using the SCF in spectrum sensing

and parameter estimation is its insensitivity to noise. Noise is stationary process, hence the SCF of noise $S_N^\alpha(f)$ is zero when $\alpha \neq 0$. Therefore, SCF provides excellent spectrum sensing and RF parameter estimation in low signal to noise ratio (SNR).

To remove the channel effect, a normalized version of the SCF called the Spectral Coherence Function (SOF) is generated:

$$C_X^\alpha(f) = \frac{S_X^\alpha(f)}{\left[S_X^0\left(f + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right)^* S_X^0\left(f - \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \right]^{1/2}} \quad (9)$$

It has been shown that the channel effects are removed from the SOF and the SOF is preserved as a reliable feature for RF parameter estimation and identification.

III. IMPLEMENTATION OF SCF/SOF ANALYSIS FOR COGNITIVE RADIO NETWORK

SCF/SOF can be used to reliably estimate and identify important RF parameters, however, it requires extremely high resolution to fully observe the cyclic frequency features [10][21]. Here, we adopt a previously developed two-stage estimation method [10] with dynamic resolution of SCF/SOF to relieve the computational burden and demonstrate it in real-time via software defined radio. In the high resolution SCF/SOF calculation stage, the computational complexity is further reduced by approximating the frequency-domain correlation matrix by a block matrix with diagonal blocks. This method is similar to the scheme proposed in [22].

Fig. 5. Implementation of SCF/SOF Analysis

Fig. 5 illustrates the software define radio implementation and the experiment setup of the SCF/SOF RF analyzer through the two-stage estimation method.

We first use Tektronix AWG7062B arbitrary waveform generator to generate input signals to the RF analyzer. The AWG7062B waveform generator is capable of generating very complex signals with controllable jitter, noise and other signal

impairments [23]. We use it to generate different kinds of primary user signals.

Second, the primary user signal is fed into a Spirent SR5500 wireless channel emulator to mimic different channels [24]. The Spirent SR5500 is a complete and efficient channel emulator that provides various built-in multi-path fading channel model, Doppler shift and additive white Gaussian noise functions.

Next, the USRP SDR receives the primary user's signal, down-converts it to baseband, and sends the baseband signal to a laptop for postprocessing. We use RFX400 USRP daughterboard in the experiments. The operation frequency range of this daughterboard is from 400 MHz to 500 MHz. For demonstration purpose, the center frequency of USRP is set to be 431 MHz with decimation rate 8. At a given time, the USRP captures signal centered at 431 MHz with 8 MHz bandwidth, and mixes it down to baseband which will be sent to the software domain for two-stage SCF/SOF analysis.

In the coarse estimation stage [10], we first obtain the spectrogram of the signal (shown in Fig. 6), so that carrier frequency \hat{f}_c and symbol rate \hat{f}_b can be coarsely estimated.

Fig. 6. Spectrogram of Received Signal

Now, fine estimation via dynamic resolution is performed after the coarse estimation of \hat{f}_c and \hat{f}_b . In previous discussion, we know that the SCF/SOF features occur around at $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = \pm 2f_c$. Therefore, there is no need to calculate the whole SCF/SOF 3-D image with the same resolution, ultra-high resolution analysis is only performed around cyclic frequencies at $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = \pm 2f_c$ (Fig. 7), leading to significant reduction in computation demand.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND REAL-TIME DEMONSTRATION

Software defined radio experiments and real-time demonstration, which is illustrated in Fig. 5, are performed to validate the effectiveness of our proposed scheme.

In example 1, we use the Tektronix AWG to generate a BPSK signal at 431.017 MHz with 4000 Hz symbol rate, and feed the signal to Spirent WCE. The WCE introduces multi-path, adds noise and provides a Doppler shift to the signal. Next, we use USRP to collect the signal centered at 431 MHz. Fig. 7 illustrates the SCF of the signal received via USRP. Now, by calculating high resolution SOF around

Fig. 7. SCF of the signal received via USRP

Fig. 8. Data Rate

coarsely estimated symbol rate and carrier frequency, we obtain accurate estimation of both parameters.

Fig. 8 to Fig. 10 show the detailed SOF of the signal in cyclic frequency domain ($f = 0$). In Fig. 8, a spectral line is observed at $\alpha = 4000 Hz$, which is the estimated symbol rate of the signal. In Fig. 9, a spectral line is observed at $\alpha = 2f_c = 34100$. The estimated baseband center frequency can then be calculated as 17050 Hz. Adding the center frequency of USRP with 431 MHz down-conversion frequency back, the estimated transmitted signal center frequency is then 431.01705 MHz. The frequency offset between estimated carrier frequency and transmitted frequency is due to the Doppler shift introduced by the channel. It is evident that an accurate center frequency is estimated.

In example 2, we use AWG to generate a QPSK modulated

Fig. 9. Estimation of Center Frequency \hat{f}_c

Fig. 11. SCF of QPSK signal received by USRP

Fig. 10. Estimation of Bit Rate \hat{f}_b

Fig. 12. Estimation of Bit Rate \hat{f}_b , QPSK

signal at 431.017 MHz and use USRP to receive the signal at 431 MHz. No Doppler shift is added in the WCE. Fig. 11 shows the SCF plot of the received signal. By zooming in the cyclic frequency projection of SOF, symbol rate f_b and carrier frequency f_c are estimated as shown in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13.

In our previously developed cognitive radio demonstration with real time video transmission in [17] and [25], we used energy/waveform based spectrum sensing. By employing the two-stage real-time SCF/SOF analysis implemented in this paper, the performance of the cognitive radio demonstration is significantly improved as well.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have implemented and demonstrated a real-time SCF/SOF RF analyzer for cognitive radio network

through software defined radio. The second-order cyclic features SCF and SOF are employed, and two-stage estimation method is applied to accurately estimate the carrier frequency and symbol rate of the primary user's signal at low computational complexity. Experiments validate the effectiveness of the proposed scheme in real time. In the future, we will implement and demonstrate the modulation identification and classification function of the intelligent spectrum sensing engine through our cyclostationary analysis based RF analyzer in real time.

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Fig. 13. Estimation of Bit Rate \hat{f}_c , QPSK

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